

Implementation of Bojonegoro Regent Regulation Number 38 of 2020 in the Implementation of Discipline and Law Enforcement of Health Protocols as an Effort to Control Covid-19

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Abstract: *Implementation of Bojonegoro Regent Regulation Number 38 of 2020 in the application of discipline and law enforcement of health protocols as an effort to control Covid-19. Stipulations and sanctions for communities or business entities that violate regulations in responding to new normal habits are contained in Bojonegoro Regent Regulation Number 38 of 2020 This study aims to determine the extent of the implementation of Bojonegoro Regent Regulation Number 38 of 2020 in the application of discipline and law enforcement of health protocols in an effort to control Covid-19. This study uses four implementation factors proposed by George Edward III, namely communication, resources, disposition and bureaucratic structure with a qualitative approach. The results of this study indicate that the operation of controlling Covid-19 optimally requires synergy, firmness of the implementor's attitude (implementors) and new innovations so that the control of Covid-19 in Bojonegoro Regency runs optimally and the Covid-19 pandemic can be over soon.*

Keywords : *Implementation, Regent Regulation, Covid-19*

I. INTRODUCTION

Countries in the world experienced serious problems at the end of 2019, including Indonesia experiencing problems with the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) at the beginning of 2020. The Covid-19 problem that started in Wuhan - China expanded and changed the order and system of government and even the world economy. Global data recorded that on February 2, 2021, there were 216 countries affected by the Covid-19 outbreak, with 103,000,000 people confirmed to be infected with Covid-19, 2,024,000 of them died and 57.3 million recovered from Covid-19. The Covid-19 outbreak that spread in Indonesia at the beginning of 2020 was always increasing, starting in early 2021 it was recorded that more than one million Indonesians were infected with the Covid-19 virus and more than 30 thousand people died.

Covid-19 caused political, social, economic, cultural shocks, and even the emergence of new habits in society. Developments at the health level have a high enough impact on the regional and national economy. The transfer of funds in dealing with Covid-19 has disrupted the country's economy, so there is a need for budget revisions and changing the provision of funds for handling Covid-19. With the distribution of vaccines, it can be used as a prevention solution as long as the Covid-19 drug has not been found, this can be used as a way out in protecting people in Indonesia.

The Bojonegoro Regency Government noted that on December 31, 2020 there were 1287 residents infected with the Covid-19 virus and 34 of them were new residents. There are 227 active patients, 967 recovered and 93 died (instagram @pemkabbojonegoro 18-02-2021, 19:45). Regarding the ever-increasing number of confirmed Covid-19 cases, the Bojonegoro Regency government is trying to improve the prevention and control of Covid-19 by issuing and enacting a Regent's Regulation to improve disciplinary compliance and

law enforcement in health protocols. The regulation is contained in the Bojonegoro Regent's Regulation Number 38 of 2020 concerning the application of discipline and law enforcement of health protocols as an effort to control Covid-19 in Bojonegoro Regency.

As for research on government regulations, where this research analyzes government policies in handling the Covid-19 pandemic (Darmin Tuwu, 2020), research that analyzes the implementation of Large-Scale Social Restrictions policies as an effort to overcome Covid-19 (Dian Herdiana, 2020). From this research, there are various approaches applied to research government policies. The results of the study are not much different, that the government's policy in preventing the transmission of Covid-19 so that it does not spread widely, the government issued a regulation. This research differs from the studies above, using a case study approach and focusing on the implementation of large-scale social restrictions in Indonesia.

There is a purpose in this study to describe and identify problems in the implementation of the Bojonegoro Regent Regulation Number 38 of 2020 on the application of discipline and law enforcement of health protocols as an effort to control Covid-19. in the implementation of the Regent's regulations related to the application of discipline.

II. METHODS

This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach, in order to understand social phenomena or symptoms by focusing on a complete picture of the implementation of the Regent's Regulation Number 38 of 2020 on the application of discipline and law enforcement of health protocols as control of Covid-19. This study focuses on the theory presented by George Edward III on policy implementation.

This study uses data samples with purposive sampling technique with several competent people to provide information about policy implementation. This study used three informants, namely key informants, main informants and supporting informants. Data collection used by interview, observation, and documentation methods.

Qualitative research in order to analyze which is based on logical arguments based on data obtained through data collection. Each category will be analyzed through a theoretical approach in order to bring up a picture that can reveal the problem. In understanding and reviewing the data obtained with an approach to program evaluation before and after.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Bojonegoro Regency, one of the regencies in East Java, has an area of 230,706 ha as reported in the Bojonegoro Regency Population and Civil Registration Service data with a population of 1,344,038 people at the end of 2020, with the addition of 12,961 people within one year. Based on the results of the study, it shows that the implementation of the Bojonegoro Regent Regulation Number 38 of 2020 in the Implementation of Discipline and Law Enforcement of Health Protocols as an Effort to Control Covid-19. Violations are still being carried out in line with the implementation of regulations related to efforts to prevent Covid-19. Handling has been carried out in a combined manner but still found people who heed the rules or regulations that have been set by the government of Bojonegoro Regency,

The approach used in analyzing the implementation of discipline and enforcement of the Health Protocol as an effort to control Covid-19 is the theory put forward by George Edward. According to Edward III's view, there are four factors that can influence the implementation of public policy including: communication factors, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure. The influence of these four factors on the implementation of discipline and law enforcement of health protocols as an effort to control Covid-19, namely:

Policy communication in the application of discipline and law enforcement of health protocols as an effort to control Covid-19 is the delivery of policy information from policy makers to policy implementers and

made it more effective by conveying it to policy target groups and other interested parties. Internal communication occurs between policy makers, namely the local government of Bojonegoro Regency, namely the Regent of Bojonegoro Regency and implementers of implementing discipline and law enforcement of health protocols as an effort to control Covid-19, including the SATPOL PP, Polri and TNI as well as the Health Service. External communication occurs between policy makers and implementers of discipline and law enforcement of health protocols to the people of Bojonegoro Regency and business entity owners and tourism managers in the Bojonegoro Regency environment. The flow of communication that occurs in policy communication is quite good, in terms of the short flow of bureaucracy. Mr. Sunarsib as the Head of Investigation and Investigation of the SATPOL PP of Bojonegoro Regency stated:

"So the flow of communication in the delivery of our duties immediately follows the instructions from the Regent regarding the implementation of discipline and law enforcement protocol mas, from us later we will carry out persuasive socialization in the village through sub-district employees and village officials. directly to comply with health protocols."(Interview with Head of Investigation and Investigation of SATPOL PP)

Resources can influence the success of policy implementation. Human resources as well as budgetary/financial resources support the implementation of policy implementation. In the implementation of law enforcement of health protocols as an effort to control Covid-19, there is a combination of various elements and elements within the Bojonegoro Regency environment including: SATPOL PP, Polri, and TNI and the people of Bojonegoro Regency as objects. As stated by Mr. Sunarsib, Head of Investigation and Investigation of SATPOL PP, Bojonegoro Regency.

"In carrying out the joint operation, we are working with the POLRES and KODIM 0813 for the joint operation of the 3 elements, yes, mas, for the socialization itself related to human resources within the scope of our employees, it is still inadequate, considering that we hold operations and socialization every day. At 09.00 WIB and 21.00 WIB, sometimes we still have difficulty in dividing the schedule of tasks and pickets".(Interview with Head of Investigation and Investigation of SATPOL PP)

Budget resources apart from relying on the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget which need to be focused and set aside to control Covid-19. The government is very focused on the interests of controlling this Covid-19. This is based on the Bojonegoro Regency Regent Regulation Number 38 of 2020, Article 10 regarding funding in the handling and control of Covid-19. All costs required in implementing the regulations are charged to: a) the Bojonegoro Regency Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget and b) Sources other lawful and non-binding provisions of laws and regulations. Quoted from the results of the press conference by the Regent of Bojonegoro, Dr. Hj. Anna Muawanah on April 14, 2020 said that:

"The funds disbursed for the handling of this covid amounted to IDR 78 billion. This fund comes from the shift in the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget plus the Village Revenue and Expenditure Budget in each village. This budget will be used to meet a number of urgent needs such as disinfectants, masks, protective equipment for health workers, as well as for the establishment of shelters and posts for handling Covid-19 in all villages and sub-districts in Bojonegoro Regency. The Bojonegoro Regency Government has also budgeted IDR 20 billion for micro-enterprises affected by Covid-19." (jatim.inews.id on 20-04-2021, 08.20)

Policy implementation cannot take place if the goals and objectives are set or identified by policy decisions. Bojonegoro Regency Regent Regulation Number 38 of 2020 Chapter 11 Article 2 is intended as the application of discipline and law enforcement of health protocols as an effort to prevent and control Covid-19 in Bojonegoro Regency. The patrol activity carried out by the SATPOL PP of Bojonegoro Regency is a tip in an effort to prevent the Covid-19 virus. The justice operation is carried out as an effort to increase public awareness about the importance of wearing masks. The general target of this judicial operation is the community of road

users and traders around roads in Bojonegoro Regency who do not comply with health protocols or do not use masks.

“The government cannot run alone without the help of various elements of society. One of them is the orderly tips for using masks when doing activities outside the home or when meeting other people and this justification operation will continue as long as there are still many violations related to health protocols.(interview with Ms. Hardianti, member of the SATPOL PP)

Based on data from the Bojonegoro Regent's Decree Number: 188/123/KEP/412,013/2020 the task force for the acceleration of handling the 2019Covid-19 in Bojonegoro Regency clearly describes the division of tasks and responsibility for the members who are included in it. With the division of tasks and from elements and elements that are 110 different but interrelated in order to accelerate the control of Covid-19. In carrying out their duties, implementors use Standard Operating Procedurethat are guided by the Bojonegoro Regent Decree Number: 188/12/KEP/412,013/2020 with specific tasks. has been determined. Where the control of Covid-19 refers to the Bojonegoro Regent's Regulation Number 38 of 2020 which aims to suppress the spread of Covid-19.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of policies in the application of discipline and law enforcement of health protocols as an effort to control Covid-19 in Bojonegoro Regency has not run optimally, because in its application the community still does not fully comply with the rules that have been implemented by the local government in accordance with Bojonegoro Regent Regulation Number 38 of 2020 (Article 6) and given punishment in accordance with the rules in the Bojonegoro Regent Regulation Number 38 of 2020 (Article 11) for those affected by judicial operations. Implementing resources in controlling Covid-19from Bojonegoro Regency are quite complex and synergistic. In carrying out the judicial operation there was a joint team from the SATPOL PP, POLRES, KODIM 0813.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Data Bappeda Kabupaten Bojonegoro, 2020
- [2] Data Dinas Kependudukan dan Pencatatan Sipil Kabupaten Bojonegoro, 2020
- [3] Herdian, Dian. 2020. Implementasi Kebijakan Pembatasan Sosial Berskala Besar (PSBB) sebagai upaya penanggulangan corona virus disease (covid-19), Vol 2, Hal 2. Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Administrasi Negara (STIA): Cimahi,
- [4] Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia, Kharisma Putra Utama, Jakarta, 2008
- [5] Keputusan Bupati Bojonegoro Nomor : 188/123/KEP/412.013/2020 Tentang Gugus Tugas Percepatan Penanganan Coronavirus Disease 2019 Kabupaten Bojonegoro, Bojonegoro
- [6] Peraturan Bupati Bojonegoro Nomor 38 Tahun Tentang Penerapan Disiplin Protokol Kesehatan Sebagai Upaya Pencegahan dan Pengendalian Covid-19 di Kabupaten Bojonegoro, Bojonegoro
- [7] Surat Edaran Kementerian Kesehatan Nomor H.K.02.01/MENKES/202/ 2020
- [8] Tuwu, Darmin. 2020. Kebijakan Pemerintah Dalam Penegakan Pandemi Covid-19, Vol 3, No 2, hal 267. Universitas Halu Oleo.